

Sprays formed by two impinging jets under flash-boiling conditions

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Abstract

Flash-boiling atomisation has received much attention in the combustion community over the past decades, and its influence on spray formation is fairly well understood. However, the vast majority of the studies have been performed on free sprays, while the effects of flash boiling on sprays formed by impinging jets are yet to be understood.

In this study, the aim was to fill this knowledge gap and evaluate the effects of flash boiling on both global structures and the droplet distribution of sprays formed by two impinging jets for rocket propulsion.

The results showed that even moderate superheating changes the global structure of the spray cloud, despite the presence of an unbroken liquid column. The colliding streams shattered and were surrounded by the recondensing vapour. Under a strong flash-boiling regime, the effects were more profound, and the interaction between two flashing jets resembled that of crossing gaseous jets. This observation, in turn, suggests the significant importance of flash-evaporated liquid in the collision process of two liquid streams formed under flash-boiling conditions. The mean droplet size was greatly reduced, and the spatial distribution of droplets within the spray cloud was deeply altered. A comparative analysis with a free jet suggested there was a dominant effect from flash boiling over the impingement, which was crucial under subcooled conditions.

Keywords: impinging jets, colliding jets, flash boiling, superheated spray, rocket injector

Introduction

Impingement of two liquid streams at the common point is an effective way to mix two different liquids [1]. This approach has been widely used in the unlike-impinging-jet injection in bi-propellant rocket engines [2]. Moreover, due to the rapid contact of the fuel with an oxidiser, such a configuration is of particular interest for hypergolic propellants [3]–[5]. However, the collision of two liquid jets is also an effective way to improve atomisation. Therefore, impinging-jet injections can also be used solely for that purpose. In that case, the streams of the same liquid are impinged together (like-impinging-jet configuration) [6]. Efficient atomisation through the collision of two liquid jets requires that the liquid streams intersect at a common point. Only then do they exchange momentum efficiently and create instabilities that cause the disintegration of the liquid streams into smaller formations, which eventually become droplets [7]. This process can be described by the dimensionless numbers [8], in particular, the jet Reynolds, Weber and Ohnesorge numbers. According to Li and Ashgriz [8], there are two main regimes and five other subregimes primarily dependent on the Reynolds number of the jet. These subregimes (with an increasing Reynolds number) are: pre-sheet formation; smooth-sheet formation; ruffled-sheet formation; open-rim-sheet formation; and for the highest Reynolds number, turbulent-sheet formation. Pre-sheet formation was observed for the very low Reynolds numbers of the jets. In that regime, two jets merged and formed a stable but ruffled sheet with no droplets detaching from its edges. In the smooth-sheet formation regime, the visible disturbances were generated in the rim (surrounding the smooth liquid sheet), which tended to grow downstream. In the ruffled-sheet regime, some disturbances observed in the sheet originated at the impingement point; however, according to the authors, the capillary instabilities were still dominant in terms of droplet generation at the rim. In the open-rim-sheet formation, the developed sheet was periodically split, but its upper part remained only ruffled and still intact. The turbulent-sheet regime formation was characterised by a strongly unstable sheet, which could not fully develop. The regimes' order remained the same regardless of the impingement angle, only the critical values of the jet Reynolds number separating the regimes were slightly different. Bush and Hasha [9] reported that different behaviour of liquid formations developed after the impingement to the jets' Weber and Reynolds numbers. For low numbers, the authors observed oscillating streams and liquid chains; while with increased values of the dimensionless numbers, the chains began to splutter. Further, the liquid sheet disintegrated and started to flap violently.

Different interactions between the jets have profound effects on the droplet formation. Yuan and Huang [10] showed that the Sauter mean diameter (SMD or D_{32}) of the sprays formed by the like-doublet, equal-momentum impinging jets was strongly dependent on the jet momentum rates. However, the curves obtained for different liquids did not overlap. Rodrigues et al. [11] indicated that increasing the Weber number reduces the number of large droplets, which leads to the reduction of the SMD. Additionally, they discussed that the jet velocity profile also had an influence on droplet diameter.

In general, the available studies on impinging-jet atomisation provide a fair understanding of the mechanisms leading to the spray formation from the two impinging jets. Besides the number of parameters, which were shown to influence those mechanisms, the Reynolds and Weber numbers of the jets are of primary importance. In practical systems, where the geometrical parameters are fixed, these dimensionless numbers can be altered by the variation of the injection velocity [9], which enables the achievement of a desired atomisation regime and spray characteristics. However, in the case of multiple-ignition rocket engines operating in space, vacuum conditions occurring during the engine restart may entirely change the liquid behaviour. Depending on the fuel and oxidiser types, flash boiling may occur. Then, the character of the liquid streams, and thus their interactions, becomes entirely different, substantially influencing the atomisation.

When a liquid is injected into environmental pressure below its vapour pressure, it becomes superheated, and vapour nucleation may appear. This nucleation process can be homogeneous or heterogeneous. Homogeneous nucleation occurs in the entire volume of the liquid; while heterogeneous nucleation is initiated at the boundaries of the liquid phase with either impurities (including dissolved gas microbubbles) or container walls [12]. There exists a theoretical thermodynamic limit to which the fluid can be brought without vaporisation. However, in practice, it is impossible to reach it because heterogeneous nucleation occurs faster. Regardless of the type of nucleation, flash boiling has been proven to strongly alter the jet and spray properties, as growing vapour bubbles lead to a disruption of initially intact liquid structures.

So far, flash boiling has been widely studied in terms of free jets and has been shown to promote the formation of smaller droplets and improve evaporation. The main research area in terms of combustion systems has been related to high-pressure fuel injection in spark ignition engines. It has been reported that flashing sprays have the potential to improve the spray quality by reducing tip penetration, decreasing droplet size, and widening the spray angle [13]–[15].

As reported by Araneo et al. [14], increasing the iso-octane temperature from 293 K to 393 K could reduce the mean diameter by about half. Xu et al. [16] reported that the overall effect of flash boiling on the droplet size was stronger for low injection pressures. The studies by Van Vuuren et al. [17], [18] for low-pressure sprays in a hot environment indicated significant changes in spray shape and a twofold reduction of the Sauter mean diameter when the liquid temperature was increased from 85 °C to 130 °C. Our previous studies [19] have shown that flash boiling had a profound influence on the spatial distribution of droplets - the droplets were more evenly distributed within the spray cloud.

As far as the impinging-jet configuration is concerned, the aspect which may strongly alter the atomisation mechanism and the mixing process is the reduced length of a liquid column. As shown in [19], the length of the column can already be strongly reduced at low-intensity flash boiling. Another effect of flash boiling on near-nozzle jet behaviour which may influence the collision is the stability of the jet. Even if it is still intact, it becomes ruffled and oscillates around the injection axis, reducing the collision probability.

In a typical impinging jet arrangement, the unbroken streams collide before they disintegrate into ligaments and droplets. Thus, disruption of the jet before the collision may change the interaction from the stream-stream to the spray-spray type. Yuan and Huang [10] forced the transition between these two types of interaction by increasing the momentum rate. As shown in their study, such a transition had profound consequences in the further evolution of the droplets, which is directly related to the jets' interaction type. However, the spray-spray interaction type can also be triggered by flash boiling. Moreover, if such a transition occurs, the structures formed by the collision of developed sprays will depend on the near-nozzle spray distribution [20]. Such a distribution, in turn, is also strongly dependent on flash boiling.

Another aspect which needs to be taken into account is the secondary effect of flash boiling on spray propagation, which may occur when the liquid is injected by an arrangement of several nozzles (e.g. multi-hole injectors). The results obtained for multi-nozzle injectors with diverging axes [19], [21]–[27] showed that the individual plumes may merge and collapse towards a centreline of the nozzle pattern and form a single jet-like spray structure. According to Xu et al. [23], such behaviour results from the interaction of overlapping plumes and momentum exchange between droplets. Jiang et al. [24] argued that the coalescence of interacting droplets and the related momentum increase in the axial directions

of the newly formed droplets were the reasons for the collapse. For impinging jets where their axes intersect, this effect may be even stronger, as droplet collisions will be more probable. Lacey et al. [28] showed that taking into account the geometrical nozzles' arrangement helps to predict the spray collapse.

The direct implementation of these observations to predict the behaviour of two impinging developed flash-boiling sprays is not possible. Firstly, as stated earlier, those observations were made for diverging nozzle arrangements. Secondly, most of those studies were conducted on multi-hole nozzles, where the liquid is already atomised immediately it exits the orifices, even under subcooled conditions. Although in the previous study [21], it was shown that the sprays in subcooled conditions characterised by long unbroken liquid columns collapse, it was evident only for the six-nozzle arrangement. In the case of a two-nozzle injector, the streams merged but did not entirely collapse. It is not clear what the effect will be in the case of intersecting jets, where the interaction between the spray plumes is expected to be much stronger, provided that the flash boiling causes the jet to break up before the impingement.

In summary, two possible effects of flash boiling can be expected on impinging jets:

1. Transition to spray-spray interaction (from the initial stream-stream interaction, due to the break-up of the liquid columns before the impingement point).
2. Less intensive (and less probable) collision of the jets, due to their oscillations (around the axis) and their ruffled surfaces.

In the first scenario, possible secondary effects may also be expected (e.g. spray collapse).

The second scenario has been shown to occur with moderate flash boiling [29]. It resulted in a considerable increase in the spray angle measured in two orthogonal directions. The signs of collision-driven wavy structures within sheets disappeared. It is not clear what will happen for more intensive flash boiling. According to Moosavian et al. [30], a gas phase generated during the injection under flash-boiling conditions becomes important. For low mass flow rates, it led to the formation of bell-shaped spray structures with reduced width (measured in the far-nozzle distance). For strong flash boiling, the vapour generation will be higher.

If at least one of these scenarios happens, it is expected that the momentum and mass exchange will be mitigated. The altered jets' interaction mechanisms will influence the downstream distribution of liquid particles and droplet statistics. In the first considered scenario, some droplets may pass the jets' intersection point without a collision; while others might coalesce. In the second scenario, the streams can either pass each other or interact partially or periodically due to the ruffled oscillating interphase, leading to intermittent, fast-changing rotations of the liquid sheet or spray [31]. Therefore, this study also aims to investigate the influence of flash boiling on the produced droplets.

1 Experimental set-up

The injection head had two cylindrical 0.7-mm nozzles arranged in a like-doublet configuration with a 30° impingement angle. The cross-section of the nozzles is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. A simplified section view through the nozzles [29]

The nozzles' length-to-diameter ratio was 5:1. The axes of the nozzles intersected 12 mm from the head. The temperature of the injected liquid was controlled indirectly by the cooling bath thermostat (Huber KISS K6), heating and circulating the silicon oil through the cooling/heating jacket in the injection head. In the experiments, deionised water was used as an injection liquid. The water was supplied to the injection head from the nitrogen-pressurised container and the pressure in the container was adjusted based on the reading from the pressure gauge (WIKA CPG1500, range: 0-10 bar). The cylindrical vessel was heated with four sleeve-type electric heaters coupled with J-type thermocouples (accuracy of ± 2.5

°C and controller accuracy of ± 1 °C). Two additional thermocouples were placed inside the vessel to monitor the liquid temperature in the centre at two different vertical locations (in the centre and at the exit from the vessel). The injection head was connected to the vessel by 4-mm (internal diameter) stainless-steel tubes wrapped with heated tapes and fibreglass insulation. Each nozzle was supplied with water by a separate tube, and each tube was of the same length. The water flow was controlled by two on/off solenoid valves (Bürkert 0255-23279), which were operated synchronously.

The nitrogen in the vessel was not separated from the liquid, as the potential impact of solubility of compressed nitrogen in water under the test conditions was considered to have a negligible effect, if any. As reported by Saddington and Kruse [32], nitrogen solubility in water decreases with temperature until the minimum solubility is reached. They found that this temperature is about 75 °C at 30.4 MPa and slightly increases for lower pressures. Therefore, the highest nitrogen concentration was expected for the subcooled conditions (approx. $9.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol_{N₂}/mol_(H₂O+N₂)). This means that in the worst-case scenario, the flash-boiling effects could be underestimated. However, this amount of dissolved nitrogen corresponds to the gas-liquid ratio of $5.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$, which is too low to cause any considerable effects on a spray cloud [33].

Table 1 shows the measurement points and investigated parameters for this study. As the temperature of the liquid was directly measured only in the vessel, the difference between the cooling oil and the liquid was determined prior to the experiment. For that purpose, high-boiling-point oil was introduced into the channels instead of water to avoid vaporisation in the channels. It could be speculated that static conditions cannot represent the dynamic injection event, and that the difference between the heating oil temperature and the flowing liquid through the channel will be different. However, the water in the tank was kept very close to the target (desired) injection liquid temperature (± 2 °C).

Table 1. Measurement points and investigated parameters

Case name	Conditions	Target injection liquid temperature [°C]	Coolant temperature [°C]	Global structures' visualisation	Droplet visualisation
Case 1	Subcooled	40	42.7	yes	yes
Case 2	Flash-boiling	140	146.4	yes	yes

1.1 Global spray visualisation

The global spray structures formed after the impingement were observed by two synchronised cameras (LaVision Imager sCMOS from two perpendicular directions. They were located at the same distance from the injection head and equipped with the same lenses (AF-S Nikkor 50 mm f/1.4G). The schematic diagram of the visualisation set-up is shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Schematic layout of the visualisation set-up for global imaging

The image resolution (2560 × 2160 pixels), the recording rate (20 Hz), and the exposure time (15 μs) were the same for both cameras, with the optics adjusted to reach the same spatial resolution (16 pixels/mm). Four LED lamps were used to illuminate the sprays. The recording captured the whole injection event, which lasted 10 s. The injection and imaging process was repeated three times for the same measurement point.

1.2 Droplet measurements

The droplet sizes were measured using a shadowgraph visualisation set-up based on an Nd:YAG laser (Spectra-Physics Quanta-Ray Pro-230), which is shown in **Figure 3**. The laser beam (532 nm) was used to excite the dye in the diffuser, producing light with a wavelength range of 574-580 nm. The generated light in the diffuser was directed through the optical fibre to the illuminating optics. The optics was positioned in front of the camera (LaVision sCMOS camera) equipped with a long-distance microscope. The injector was placed between the camera and the illuminating optics, so the light emitted by the optics travelled through the spray. The field of view was 10 x 8.6 mm, with its centre in the axis of the injection head. The spatial resolution was 4 μm per pixel. The depth of the field was calibrated using a plate with model droplets ranging from 10 to 200 μm , where the plate was moved from -10 to 10 mm from the focal plane. Based on the detection ability of the droplets outside the focal plane, correction factors for different droplet size groups were established. The camera, injector, and laser were synchronised to operate at a frequency of 10 Hz. Subsequently, the image acquisition started 10 ms after the start of the injection to limit it exclusively to stable, fully developed spray. The recordings were repeated three times for each measurement point. Each time, 36 frames were captured, totalling 108 frames for three repetitions.

Figure 3. Schematic layout of the visualisation set-up for droplet measurements

2 Results

The results from each measurement campaign performed with different experimental set-ups are presented in the following separate subsections.

2.1. Global spray visualisation

The impinging-jet sprays were visualised from two perpendicular directions, and some selected results of that visualisation are shown in **Figure 4**. The single jet (visualised for comparison purposes) was observed only from one side, and the corresponding case images are also presented in **Figure 4**. Note that the single jet images were rotated, so the jet's axis was in accordance with the vertical direction of the images. Looking at the spray generated by a single stream under flash-boiling conditions, one can observe a substantial near-nozzle jet angle increase. This widening of the spray causes them not to collide at a single point, in the case of the impinging jets, but to interact over a bigger area. Therefore, it might be expected that the fluid elements which collide outside the geometrical intersection point of the nozzles' axes (especially on the sides of that point) will exchange momentum in such a way that the transverse velocity vectors will be increased. These vectors are schematically shown in **Figure 4** with red arrows (camera 2, flash-boiling case).

The structure formed under such conditions did not resemble the collapsed spray and was similar to that observed for two crossing gas jets [34], [35]. As shown by Disimile et al. [34], two colliding turbulent air jets merge into a single structure with an elliptical cross-section, with the major axis perpendicular to the jets' plane. Although the exact cross-section shape in the impingement area is not known, the images taken from both directions confirm that the width of the spray cloud in the collision area is wider in the direction perpendicular to the jets' plane (Fig. 2, camera 2). A similar pattern was observed in the collision of two laminar pre-vaporised propane-butane jets in [35]. Despite the much lower Reynolds

number, the analogy to the structures generated by two flashing liquid jets observed here in this study is evident. The two gas jets collided and significantly expanded perpendicular to the jets' plane.

Figure 4. Instantaneous spray images

Combining these observations with our previous research [21], which showed that flash-vaporised liquid plays an important role in the alteration of the flow conditions within the spray cloud, it is likely that the vaporised liquid also plays an important role here. Moreover, it was revealed that even under moderate flash-boiling conditions, a condensing vapour can appear around the liquid jet. This observation was confirmed later for exactly the same injection set-up [29].

Under strong flash-boiling conditions, the amount of evaporated liquid will be increased. Moreover, as the droplets are distributed over a larger volume (wider cone of the jets), their collision is presumably less probable. Therefore, it could be speculated that the interaction between the two colliding flashing jets observed here is driven by the vapour components present in these jets.

2.2 Droplet measurements

The droplet sizes were determined from the shadowgraph images. The image processing was performed in several steps. First, a strict sliding maximum filter was used to normalise the image intensity and minimise variations in the illumination light (due to laser power fluctuations) between the frames. The normalisation radius was ten pixels. Next, the images were divided by a reference image, resulting in locally normalised images for further processing. These normalised images were then converted to black-and-white versions. Additionally, a minimum shadow slope of 15% of the maximum intensity per pixel was applied to distinguish the particles located near and far from the focal plane. It was done to include only shadows with sharp edges, since processing those with diffused edges could result in misleading shadowed areas.

After capturing a total of 108 frames across three repetitions, the images were processed together, and the droplets were analysed to construct droplet size distributions. The distributions obtained for the impinging jets and the single jets under subcooled conditions are shown in **Figure 5**. The data indicate that the fraction of the smaller particles (10-20 μm) for subcooled conditions is higher for impinging jets, which directly results from the impingement-driven break-up. For flash-boiling conditions, it is the opposite - the fraction of the smaller particles is higher for the single-jet case. This, in turn, could be the effect of the droplets' coalescence.

The observed importance of flash-evaporated liquid in the collision processes and the forming of global spray structures (reported in the previous subsection) does not mean that the highly dispersed droplets (within wider and conical jets due to flash boiling) do not collide and coalesce. It may only be expected that their interactions will be less probable. However, when this scenario takes place, and the small droplets (smaller due to flash-boiling-driven break-up) collide, it is more likely that they will coalesce rather than break up into smaller parts, as the small droplets have a much lower momentum.

Figure 5. Droplet size distribution for the doublet and the single jet, respectively from the left

Consequently, the relative reduction of SMD due to flash boiling is smaller for the impinging jets (Figure 6). This effect is also observed for other statistical droplet parameters, such as: D43 (volume-weighted mean diameter); D10 (number-weighted mean diameter); Dv10 (tenth percentile of volume distribution); Dv50 (volume median diameter); and Dv90 (ninetieth percentile of volume distribution). It also needs to be noted that in the case of impinging jets, the subcooled sprays were characterised by smaller diameters compared to the subcooled free jets. Nevertheless, regardless of the lower reference values of the impinging-jet sprays (measured for subcooled conditions), the absolute values for the flashing impinging-jet sprays were higher than for the analogous free jets. This indicates the presence of the coalescence effect.

Figure 6. Statistical droplet parameters for the doublet and the single jet, respectively from the left

The outcome of the efficient interaction between the jets impinging under subcooled conditions can also be seen in raw droplet images (Figure 7). The relative reduction of the droplet sizes (due to the flash boiling) for a single jet was probably even stronger than reported in Figure 6. As may be observed in Figure 7, the image for a single-jet injection under subcooled conditions is characterised by the presence of highly deformed droplets and large ligaments. Those structures were recognised by the image processing algorithm but were not included in the distributions presented in Figure 5, nor in the statistical droplet parameters presented in Figure 6. Calculating the volumes of such liquid structures is not possible based only on shadows determined from a single observation direction. Therefore, the results presented in Figure 5 and Figure 6 were obtained only for the droplets characterised by the perimeter-to-diameter ratio of 100-110% of that for a circle.

Figure 7. *Instantaneous droplet images*

As reported by Yuan and Huang [10], the complicated mixing behaviour of two conventionally developed sprays was mainly controlled by the collision probability of the droplets and the Weber number of the droplets' lateral motion: that is, the interactions between droplets in the spray. Therefore, with different flash-boiling intensities, one may expect different behaviour from the impinging jets, as that intensity strongly affects droplet dispersion in the free sprays [19].

Conclusions

This study documented different effects from flash boiling on impinging jets and a single jet. However, caution is required when extending these observations to all impinging-jet configurations, as the impingement process depends on many parameters, including impingement angle, number of nozzles, internal design, and dimensionless numbers such as Reynolds and Weber numbers.

The global imaging results showed that due to the flash boiling, the jets disintegrated before the impingement point. Therefore, for the high-temperature injection, the interaction changed to spray-spray type from the initial collision of two liquid columns (observed under subcooled conditions).

Moreover, the flash-boiling generated sprays were accompanied by a large amount of rapidly evaporated water (manifested by an increased amount of condensation nuclei increasing the scattering signal), which had further consequences on the interactions between the two colliding jets.

It is important to highlight that under flash-boiling conditions, the sprays did not collapse. Instead, a strong widening in one direction was observed for the impinging jets. The large amount of flash-evaporated liquid presumably caused the transition from structures typical for impinging liquid jets into structures similar to those observed by other researchers for crossing gaseous jets.

For both single-stream and impinging jets, the spray area was increased under flashing conditions, which resulted from the enhanced droplet dispersion already near the nozzles (due to flash-boiling induced break-up, which is also a source of additional axial momentum).

It may be concluded that despite the widening of the jets and their break-up before the interaction zone, reducing the probability of droplet collisions, the momentum exchange between the jets colliding under flash-boiling conditions was efficient. The two jets of vapour and finer droplets propagated in a parallel direction to the jets' plane, changing their initial propagation direction due to the impingement.

Despite the strong effect of the flash boiling on the global structures formed by two impinging jets, the relative effect on droplet sizes was limited - it was smaller than for a single jet and most probably was

caused by the coalescence of the droplets. The smaller droplets are more prone to coalesce, as their momentum is expected to be much smaller.

It needs to be emphasised that the effects of flash boiling on sprays, which are initially (under subcooled conditions) characterised by the presence of unbroken liquid columns, depend on the flash-boiling intensity. Therefore, the observations here are not universal for all flash-boiling regimes. Moreover, as shown by Limbu [20], the overall structures formed by colliding developed sprays are dependent on the near-nozzle spray distribution. This distribution, in turn, will be dependent on the flash-boiling intensity. Thus, it can be expected that not only the possible transition from stream-stream to spray-spray type interaction should be taken into account, but also the intensity of the flash boiling, as it will influence the collisions and mixing process. This aspect is to be investigated as the next step.

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